

Electrochemical Reactions at Sacrificial Electrodes. Part-VIII. Synthesis of Aluminium Alkoxides and their Coordination Compounds

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Aluminium alkoxides, Al(OR)_3 (R = methyl, ethyl, n-propyl, n-butyl and n-amyl groups), have been synthesised by the direct electrochemical technique. Though these alkoxides do not form coordination compounds when refluxed with 1,10-phenanthroline, yet coordination compounds of all these alkoxides have been synthesised with 1,10-phenanthroline by the electrochemical method. The products have been characterised by elemental analysis and infrared spectral data. Current efficiencies of all these systems are quite high.

Direct electrochemical synthesis of metal alkoxides have been reported recently from our laboratories¹. In continuation of our interest in this area, we report the electrochemical synthesis of aluminium alkoxides and their coordination compounds in this communication. These alkoxides are widely used as catalysts in several organic reactions².

of methanol, ethanol, n-propanol, n-butanol and n-pentanol at sacrificial aluminium anode and inert platinum cathode yield aluminium alkoxides (equations 1 and 2) :

At the inert platinum cathode :

At the sacrificial aluminium anode :

Results and Discussion

Aluminium alkoxides : Electrochemical reactions

The electrolysis characteristics of these reactions

TABLE-1 ELECTROLYSIS CHARACTERISTICS, ANALYTICAL AND OTHER RELATED DATA OF THE ELECTROLYSIS OF ALCOHOL AND (ALCOHOL + LIGAND) AT ALUMINIUM ANODE

Alcohol	Potential V	Colour	Product	Al% : Found/(Calcd.)
Methanol	30	White	$\text{Al(OCH}_3)_3$	21.1(22.5)
Ethanol	30	White	$\text{Al(OC}_2\text{H}_5)_3$	16.1(16.7)
n-Propanol	50	White	$\text{Al(OC}_3\text{H}_7)_3$	13.1(13.2)
n-Butanol	40	White	$\text{Al(OC}_4\text{H}_9)_3$	11.2(11.0)
n-Pentanol	50	White	$\text{Al(OC}_5\text{H}_{11})_3$	9.9(9.4)
Methanol + 1,10-Phen.	30	Dirty white	$(\text{H}_3\text{CO})_3\text{Al.C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$	9.0(9.0)
Ethanol + 1,10-Phen.	30	Dirty white	$(\text{H}_5\text{C}_2\text{O})_3\text{Al.C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$	7.7(7.9)
n-Propanol + 1,10-Phen.	30	Dirty white	$(\text{H}_7\text{C}_3\text{O})_3\text{Al.C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$	7.5(7.0)
n-Butanol + 1,10-Phen.	40	Dirty white	$(\text{H}_9\text{C}_4\text{O})_3\text{Al.C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$	6.3(6.4)
n-Pentanol + 1,10-Phen.	40	Dirty white	$(\text{H}_{11}\text{C}_5\text{O})_3\text{Al.C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$	5.6(5.8)

are listed in Table 1. All these products are white in colour and are very less soluble in the commonly used organic solvents.

Aluminium contents in these compounds have been determined by the oxine method³. The percentage of aluminium in these compounds (Table 1) corresponds to 3 : 1 stoichiometry of the alcohol and aluminium. This indicates that the protons of the alcohol molecules have been replaced by the anodic aluminium and thus forming aluminium-oxygen linkage in the products.

Infrared spectral data of the products reveal that there is no absorption band corresponding to the hydroxyl group⁴, i.e. in the range 3 200–3600 cm^{-1} . However, the characteristic bands of all the products appear at 1 000–1 116 and 675–725 cm^{-1} . Survey of literature^{5,6} reveals that the $\nu_{(\text{C-O})\text{M}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ stretching modes in the metal alkoxides appear at 1 000–1 160 and 400–600 cm^{-1} respectively. Recently, Aggarwal and Mehrotra⁷ reported some bimetallic alkoxides of cadmium and aluminium. These workers assigned the bands at 950–1 051 and 695–730 cm^{-1} to $\nu_{(\text{C-O})\text{Al}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Al-O}}$ stretching modes respectively. Thus the above bands of the present products can be assigned to $\nu_{(\text{C-O})\text{Al}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Al-O}}$ stretching vibrations. Generally, metal alkoxides have polymeric structure due to alkoxy bridging^{5,6,8}. Insoluble behaviour of the electrochemical products and the appearance of $\nu_{(\text{C-O})\text{Al}}$ band in the lower region⁸ indicate the existence of these aluminium alkoxides as polymers.

Current efficiencies of these systems have also been determined and it has been observed that these vary from 0.75 to 0.98 g eq. per Faraday. This shows that the reactions (equations 1 and 3) leading to the formation of aluminium alkoxides, are the predominant reactions of these systems.

Coordination compounds of aluminium alkoxides : The aluminium alkoxides prepared by the electrochemical methods have been refluxed with 1,10-

phenanthroline in polar as well as in non-polar solvents for several hours. The elemental analysis of the products, however, reveals that 1,10-phenanthroline molecules could not rupture the alkoxy bridges in the aluminium alkoxide molecules to form their coordination compounds. 1.0 g of the ligand has, therefore, been added to the alcohols in addition to the supporting electrolyte (Bu_4NCl). This solution was then electrolysed at aluminium anode so that the ligand molecule may be added to the alkoxides before these could polymerise through alkoxy bridges. The electrolysis characteristics are summarised in Table 1. The white compounds separated in the anode compartment are also insoluble in the common organic solvents and are not affected much by moisture and air. The products do not melt upto 150° but show slight colour change at about 200°.

Aluminium contents in the electrochemical products (Table 1) correspond to the molecular formula, $\text{Al}(\text{OR})_3 \cdot \text{L}$, showing 1 : 3 : 1 stoichiometry of aluminium, alcohol and ligand.

Infrared spectra of these compounds exhibit characteristic $\nu_{(\text{C-O})\text{Al}}$ bands⁵⁻⁷ at 980–1 130 cm^{-1} and $\nu_{\text{Al-O}}$ bands^{6,7} at 600–715 cm^{-1} . Comparison of the ir spectra of these compounds with the parent alkoxides reveals that the $\nu_{(\text{C-O})\text{Al}}$ bands in these compounds appear in a slightly higher region as compared to the parent alkoxides and distinctly two or three absorption bands appear in this region. Shift of these bands towards the higher region shows the coordination of the ligand to aluminium.

Appearance of the $\nu_{(\text{C-O})\text{Al}}$ bands around 1 000 cm^{-1} shows the presence of alkoxy bridging^{5,6,8} in these compounds. Thus the ligand molecules could not rupture all the alkoxy bridging in the present alkoxides and these coordination compounds still exist as polymers. The polymeric nature of these compounds is also indicated by their insoluble behaviour.

Current efficiencies of all these systems are

also quite close to 100% showing that the reactions leading to the formation of the coordination compounds of aluminium alkoxides are the predominant reactions of these systems.

The present study thus presents a simple and direct electrochemical method for the synthesis of aluminium alkoxides and their coordination compounds. The method is associated with quite high values of current efficiencies.

Experimental

Methanol, ethanol, n-propanol, n-butanol and n-pentanol were purified by the usual methods⁹. Tetrabutylammonium chloride (Reidel, Pure) was crystallised from conductivity water and dried under reduced pressure at 100°. It was used as supporting electrolyte in the electrochemical reactions. 1,10-Phenanthroline (Merck, Extrapure) was used as such.

H-Type cell made of Pyrex glass was used to conduct the electrochemical reactions. The cathode and anode compartments were separated from each other by a sintered glass disc of G-3 porosity. The volume of the anode compartment was more than double the volume of the cathode compartment. Both the compartments were provided with two outlets each, one for the guard-tube and the other for the electrode. The outlets for electrodes were sealed after fitting the electrodes in order to carry the reaction in an inert atmosphere.

Platinum foil ($1 \times 1 \times 0.005 \text{ cm}^3$) was used as cathode and aluminium foil ($10 \times 2 \times 0.02 \text{ cm}^3$) as anode. Direct current was obtained with the help of Toshniwal electrophoresis power supply.

Procedure : Alcohol (whose alkoxide is to be synthesised) containing tetrabutylammonium chloride (0.005 M) as supporting electrolyte was taken in the electrolysis cell. Aluminium and platinum foils were dipped in the anode and cathode compartments respectively. Necessary connections were made with the power supply and

potential across the electrodes was then adjusted so that a current of about 20 mA passed through the cell,

where, $\text{Al}_{(+)}$ is aluminium anode and $\text{Pt}_{(-)}$ is platinum cathode. Electrolysis was carried out for about 8 h with continuous stirring in the anode compartment at room temperature. White solids that separated out in the anode compartment were filtered, washed repeatedly with dry ether and dried at reduced pressure in an all-glass filtration unit. All efforts were made to protect the products from air and moisture.

In case of the synthesis of the coordination compounds of aluminium alkoxides, 1,10-phenanthroline (1.0 g) was also added in the anode compartment in addition to the supporting electrolyte before starting the electrolysis process. The other details were essentially the same as discussed above for the synthesis of aluminium alkoxides.

Current efficiencies of these systems were determined by conducting the reactions for exactly 2 h when a current of 20 mA was passed through the solution. The solution in the anode compartment was first distilled off and then evaporated to dryness. The ratio of the amount of aluminium in the dry mass and the theoretical amount of aluminium dissolved, gave the current efficiency of the reaction.

Aluminium contents in the products were determined by heating to dryness the weighed amount of the product with fuming nitric acid four times. The dry mass was then dissolved in a few drops of dilute HCl and aluminium in the solution was estimated volumetrically with oxine³.

Infrared spectra (nujol) were obtained on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Sodium chloride plates and polythene films were used to record the spectra in the regions 4000–600 and 600–200 cm^{-1} respectively.

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